

THE JEWELRY OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES, THE PLACE OF THE HERITAGE OF ALISHER NAVOI IN HUMAN SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHILD EDUCATION ISSUES IN HIS WORKS

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Abstract. *Alisher Navoi is one of the great people who played a great role in the world civilization and the historical development of our nation, as well as the rise of science. Alisher Navoi's legacy had a strong influence on the rise of our national spirituality and the formation of the worldview and civilization of our people's thinking. Navoi aimed to establish the most just and mature society based on the perfection of people. He calls people to understand themselves, to realize their social duty and fulfill it seriously. Navoi pays attention to the formation of the growing young generation into a well-rounded person, to their self-education, to understanding and correcting their mistakes and shortcomings. In Navoi's works, it is recommended to use the model method of dealing with child education in the family and at school.*

Keywords: *development, poetry, people's ancestors, contribution, prestigious, virtues such as goodness.*

The great sage, thinker, statesman, sultan of poetry Nizamiddin Mir Alisher Navoi for honoring the memory of our people's ancestors, honoring our national values, high spirituality, and his great contribution to the development of poetry, literature, especially the Turkish language. always in honor. In the works of Alisher Navoi, virtues such as goodness, patriotism, bravery, generosity, and beauty are always at the forefront. We are talking about the prestigious name of Navoi, the immortality of his creative heritage, the artistic genius that knows no boundaries of time and space. We always speak with pride.

Alisher Navoi is a great person who forms an entire era in the history of our nation's consciousness and thinking, artistic culture, an incomparable representative of our national literature, an immortal artist of words who glorified the pride and honor of our nation to the world. In other words, there is not a single person who speaks Turkish and Persian in the world who does not know Navoi, does not love Navoi, does not look at Navoi with loyalty and faith. At this place, the first President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, praised our great grandfather Mir Alisher Navoi, saying, "If we call this great man a saint, he is a saint of saints, if we say a thinker, he is a thinker of thinkers, if we say a poet, he is a sultan of poets."¹

If we talk about the question of the human factor and the role of individuals in the process of the historical development of human society, the activities of great people are understood. Such persons also have qualities typical of the people who raised them from among themselves. In addition to realizing the identity of a great person, protecting national and state independence, making one's people happy and raising their development to a high level, it is important to provide valuable support to universal human abilities and the overall development of the entire human society. takes place.

That is why the study and research of the spiritual heritage of such persons has always been relevant.

Alisher Navoi is one of the great people who played a great role in the world civilization and the historical development of our nation, as well as the rise of science. Alisher Navoi's legacy had a strong impact on the rise of our national spirituality and the formation of the worldview and civilization of our people's thinking. When Alisher Navoi worked in the positions of seal, mayor and minister, he spared no effort to improve the people's life, he was engaged in beautification and construction works. In addition, it is detailed in historical and scientific works that he built roads, bridges, houses, mosques, schools, madrasas, baths and hospitals with his own funds.

It can be seen from this that our great thinker grandfather, in addition to promoting knowledge and enlightenment, creativity, benevolence, generosity, high moral and human virtues in his works, he himself we will see that he followed the verses. This shows the unity of words and work in the activity of Alisher Navoi.

Alisher Navoi's legacy is so great that his works cover literary studies, philosophy, political science, ethics, linguistics, history and many other areas of society. The ideas he put forward in his works about the essence of existence, things and events, human maturity, morals, role in the development of society, manners, qualities of perfection, the importance of education in raising a well-rounded person are not only It has not lost its importance in the education of young people even today.

We need to understand Alisher Navoi not only as the founder of classical Uzbek literature, a genius poet, a famous statesman, a patron of education and art, but also as an encyclopedic thinker who formed a whole Renaissance period in the history of our national spirituality.

From these thoughts of Abdurahim Erkayev², it can be understood that our thinker grandfather paid a lot of attention to deep philosophical observations and moral ideas and social phenomena in the life of society in his works. To give a brief explanation, Alisher Navoi is one of the great people who, in addition to making an incomparable contribution to the development of our nation's literature with his creativity, had a great impact on the spirituality, culture and development of the peoples living in Movarounnahr and Khorasan.

The importance of the spiritual heritage of Alisher Navoi in the education of children is to satisfy their aesthetic and artistic needs, enrich their knowledge and worldview, sharpen their minds, enhance their taste, realize their identity, enjoy our national spiritual heritage and be nourished by it, in a word. In other words, it plays an important role in the development of a person who is morally mature and has his own place and direction in society.

Looking at the legacy of Alisher Navoi, we can see that the essence of his works includes ideas aimed at perfecting tolerance, initiative and patriotism. The spiritual heritage of the thinker-genius poet has not lost its importance during the historical development of the human society, has spread widely among peoples, has become a school for creative people, and is an effective tool of the educational process.

Regardless of the genre of literature or the field of science, the works of our thinker and poet grandfather, in their true essence, glorify human perfection, perfection, morals, education and enlightenment. it is emphasized that science is the main support in the life of man and

society. At the same time, it glorifies human qualities such as generosity, love, honesty, diligence, honesty and intelligence.

Today, respect for the inexhaustible genius of our great ancestors and interest in studying their rich scientific heritage is increasing in foreign countries. The confirmation of this can be seen in the examples of scientific and artistic works published in different countries of the world about their life and work, as well as monuments erected in memory of our great ancestors.

In Alloma's works, the methods, and means of forming a perfect person are also expressed. In Navoi's works, it is recommended to use the model method of dealing with child education in the family and at school. Education and training should be carried out by parents and teachers. Alisher Navoi advises children not to punish physically, but to treat them politely, but not to exceed the norm. It is known that Navoi encouraged the teacher to be demanding, but emphasized the need to know a certain standard in both. Speaking about education, he said, "Not to educate one's ability is oppression, education to the incompetent is a shame." "Don't destroy him by not educating him, don't destroy your education because of it."

Navoi pays attention to the formation of the growing young generation into a well-rounded person, to their self-education, to understanding and correcting their mistakes and shortcomings.

Alisher Navoi also expresses important thoughts about the ways of acquiring knowledge. He says that it is necessary to constantly learn knowledge. It emphasizes that it is possible to overcome any difficulty, to work diligently, to act diligently, to work consistently, to finish it, to learn with patience and perseverance. So, the great scholar correctly expressed the principles of learning in his time and even defined the education system, that is, Alisher Navoi praised the education system in his time, studying in madrasas, or being a scientist, craftsman, advises artists to take advantage of opportunities to learn by becoming an apprentice or independently. The thinker emphasizes the need for teachers-domlas, mudarris and mentors-mentors to be knowledgeable and educated when providing deep knowledge to young people. He criticizes ignorant, bigoted and ignorant teachers and says that it is necessary for a teacher to be an educated teacher who knows the ways of teaching. For example, in the work "Mahbub ul-Qulub", while thinking about school teachers, he condemns their strictness, ignorance and greed, he objectively evaluates the burden of the teacher's work and the training fee.

So, Navoi shows the importance of science in the intellectual maturity of every young person, and the science is considered the basis of the development of the society, the people of knowledge, the spreader of knowledge.

scholar—he also pays attention to the issues of respect for the virtuous and improving their standard of living.

In his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub", Navoi reflected the qualities characteristic of a perfect person of his time and explained their purpose and essence.

In the second part of the book, "Khamida ad'ol va zamima khaisal khasiyat", which revealed the essence of voluntary qualities that depend on the mental state of a person, such as contentment, patience, manners, love "He is open-minded, clear-eyed, and worthy of attention. Patience is a high human virtue that gives strength to contentment. Patience leads a person to perfection," he says.

Also, the poet's masterpiece "Hamsa", consisting of five epics, covers all issues of human development.

Navoi aimed to establish the most just and mature society based on the perfection of people. He calls people to understand themselves, to realize their social duty and fulfill it seriously: "El netib topkai mine, I don't find myself. I wander in the wilderness of love and madness..." ("Lisonut-tayr" Alisher Navoi).

In order to reach the level of perfection, a person must try to be physically and spiritually clean, with outward - external purification, to reach the main internal purity and to reach the state of purity of heart - not having prejudice against any being and thing. Navoi gives a very high assessment to the ability of the individual and puts forward the idea that he can understand the essence of the world: "Think about your body, whatever you want, you want from yourself."

"Hayratul-Abror" includes twenty more articles besides three surprises, the main content of which is these articles.

Article 18 (The value of life). If a person is able to control himself, if he easily forgives the horrors of the environment, if he does not give in to pains and sorrows, his life will be happy. The highest blessing, the greatest wealth dedicated to man is the mind, thinking, - says the poet. Navoi's advices in this article are healthy opinions that emerged from observing life events.

Alisher Navoi advocates the need to learn a profession in this world, just as Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband demanded of those who came to accept muridship. Even a person who has lived without learning a profession is like a person who left the house of the world sad.

The words "Kamol et kasb" can be understood both as "acquire to mature" and as "accomplish learning a profession". Both of them envisage a person's desire to achieve perfection in this world. Learning a profession is also a step towards perfection. Shu also interprets the conditions of "start-ba-kor" as "Knowledge and wisdom are the adornment of a man."

A. Navoi's epic "Hayratul Abror" describes the moral qualities of a perfect person, such as goodness, generosity, purity, modesty, kindness, thoughtfulness, manners, tolerance, humility, honesty, and justice, and the ways of spiritual perfection are analyzed.

A. Navoi "If you want to pass the world without sorrow, knowledge is a skill learned." In his opinion, it is important to educate the young generation to become people-loving, educated people with the best qualities. Education plays a leading role in this. At the same time, he believes that it is possible to correct bad-behaved children, just as there are capable students, who are influenced by education.

In conclusion, it can be said that the wide promotion of Alisher Navoi's works is important for the formation of high human and noble qualities such as patriotism, initiative, creativity, tolerance in the members of the society, for raising children with national moral norms, for developing a broad worldview and intellectual potential. serves to increase the efficiency of our work.

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